

Model covariate maps and partial dependence plots

The graphs below are partial dependence plots for each of our variables for each species. They show the relationship between the variable and bird abundance (\hat{y}). The percentages underneath the graphs show the variable importance. For the non-climate variables, the covariate maps used to train the model are also included. No covariate maps are included for the climate variables since these varied from year to year.

Climate

Land use

All covariate maps shown are for the current situation.

Covariate map	Blackbirds	Mallards	House sparrows
Arable 500m buffer			

Vegetative cover

All covariate maps shown are for the current situation.

Other

Covariate map	Blackbirds	Mallards	House sparrows
Altitude			

Dataset: France

